

Abstract

Overview of the Regulatory Framework for Medicines and Health Products in Portugal.

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Abstract

The regulatory framework for medicines and health products – assumed, for the purposes of this overview, to include cosmetics, medical devices, and food supplements – is primarily based on the legal framework of the European Union, complemented by specific national legislation. Its fundamental objective is to ensure high standards of quality, efficacy, and safety.

Medicines for human use are regulated by INFARMED – the National Authority for Medicines and Health Products, I.P., which plays a central role in the evaluation, authorisation, and surveillance of these products. Specific regulatory regimes apply to homeopathic medicines, which may benefit from simplified registration procedures, and to traditional herbal medicines, whose authorisation is based on well-established traditional use and specific safety and quality criteria (see Decree-Law No. 176/2006 – Medicinal Products Act). (Note: Veterinary medicines follow a distinct regulatory framework, aligned with Regulation (EU) 2019/6, and will not be addressed in this overview).

Cosmetic products are regulated under Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 / Decree-Law No 23/2025, with a focus on consumer safety and the responsibilities of economic operators, and do not require prior marketing authorisation. Medical devices (MDs), including in vitro diagnostic medical devices (IVDs), are currently governed by Regulations (EU) 2017/745 and 2017/746, which set enhanced requirements for clinical evaluation, traceability, and post-marketing surveillance. These product categories are also subject to regulatory oversight by INFARMED.

Finally, food supplements fall under food law (Decree-Law No. 118/2015) and are primarily regulated by the Directorate-General for Food and Veterinary (DGAV), with an emphasis on composition and labelling, and may not bear therapeutic claims.

This integrated framework highlights the complexity and diversity of health products available on the Portuguese market, with particular emphasis on key aspects: (a) the differences between medicines and medical devices in terms of their mechanisms of action; (b) the distinction between “therapeutic indications” (applicable to medicines and medical devices) and “health claims” (applicable to food supplements); and (c) the specific regulatory features of homeopathic and traditional herbal medicines compared with other medicinal products.

Keywords: INFARMED; DGAV; Regulatory Affairs; Medical Devices; Food Supplements; Traditional Herbal Medicines; EU Legislation.

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